

20 November 1972

Dear Andrew,

Karen F. wrote me a cordial if noncommittal note saying she was leaving very soon for Oman and hoping to talk to me there. Sends her best regards to you whom she remembered in Abu Dhabi.

Also got overdue letter from Director of Information, Muscat who said that there was no objection to the three of us coming to Oman to survey but preferred we come in April [I gather it's hot then and I don't want to wait that long if possible] and wrote. The Director of I of also asked for "few details please". So I wrote and thanked him for the permit as it were, gave details of an area as I wish + my keeping south-east of Karen and you wanting to go on the coast from Muscat to the NW and also SE to SW. Hope I didn't say the wrong thing from your point of view but I felt I had better make it clear we weren't going to tread on Karen's toes. I won't bother you with all the area details but I asked for the coast for you, the area would be from Muscat to the interior, the Tabal Al-Dhala and the foothills from the T. Adhbar SE to SW. where I gather is the limit of friendly inhabitants. Doubt something can be negotiated in Muscat. Karen probably has opted for a more likely area but that's her reward for being there first. I hope, probably in vain, to hear something further by this weekend and will let you know directly.

I spoke to Karl about a transit. He says he's got \$350 to spend on one, won't buy a leveling rod as he has one at home.

Karl claims he can get a Top instrument for \$50. I don't know. However I tried briefly to convince him of the merits of a very good instrument second hand. He might go for it but won't have money until after Dec. I believe he will be in London next week for British Academy lectures he's giving. If you run into him you might bring up the transit again.

By the way, Karl said he didn't know what you thought about Dashi & Sekh and was going to write to find out if you still wanted to do it. I said I thought you rather felt ~~you were~~ that it was all settled for you to ~~and~~ go to DD again, which seemed pleasing to L-K. Anyhow you can tell him different when he writes if you want.

Best regards

J.